

An Analysis of Importance given to Training based on Demographic profile of Employees for better Employee Engagement

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1.INTRODUCTION TO THE STUDY

In this complex and robust environment, organizations must boost its employee's performances. To overcome and sustain in this critical market organizations, need to initiate better workplace practices. According to Rashid et al. 2011, when employees are satisfied and contented, they work with high commitment levels leading to increased individual and organizational performances. Organizations which understand that their support and effective management practices help their employees achieve desired results are more successful. Lock Wood, 2007 stated that organizational environment plays a vital role by adapting useful tools and measurements that provide good results by increasing employee role clarity, intention to stay, and organizational citizenship behavior.

When employees show a positive attachment with their job, it can be observed that the organization has committed workforce leading to engagement. Employee engagement is an emotional, behavioral, and physiological commitment employees give to the organization. Employees intend to go above the desired levels and fulfill organizational goals. Further focusing on employee engagement and its importance, organization started segmenting their employees based on their demographic profiles. Segmentation helps in identifying the key variables in managing employee commitment and productivity levels.

Employee engagement being the main idea in the current study. Researcher critically examined the concept and various drivers of engagement. Organizations should develop employee engagement level by initiating and enhancing the practices leading to engagement. As engagement is not an event but rather practice, it needs to be managed systematically. The drivers of engagement and employee outcomes need to be analyzed to study how the engagement drivers impact employee outcome levels.

On the other hand, Bhatia, 2011 states that among professionals, researchers, and managers employee engagement has become one of the important concepts to practice. Also, according to Kumar & Swetha 2011 organizations that provide an effective environment to develop employee

engagement levels among its employees boost outcomes, challenging the competitors. Rashid et al. 2011, stated that organizations need to build effective practices to occupy top positions leaving competitors behind. Employee engagement being an effective technique for attaining global advantage, it has become a prominent requirement to achieve effective employee outcomes fostering high levels of employee and business performances.

According to the report of Talent map, 2017, employee engagement has become a benchmark study for all the organizations irrespective of their type and size as the report shows that the engagement score is 86% among the organizations with employee strength of less than 250 and is 71% among mid-sized and large organizations thus this study is focused towards small and medium IT companies.

Due to the fast and effective expansion of IT organizations in India, the relationships with nearby countries became closer. This helped to generate huge employment for Indians. On the other hand, the financial crisis highly impacted the IT companies. As a result of this, the recruitment/ hiring in different sectors are reported with low headcounts decreasing the organizational productivity. Organizations need to reinvent themselves by implementing effective, innovative and competitive practices. Robinson et.al, 2004 stated that, in today's modern IT world for organizations employee engagement plays a vital role.

1.1 DESCRIPTION OF VARIABLES

Independent Variables:

- a) Gender
- b) Age
- c) Educational Qualifications
- d) Marital Status
- e) Years of Experience

Dependent Variables:

- a) Training
- b) Communication
- c) Leadership
- d) Compensation
- e) Work-life balance

1.2 Research Question Which demographic variable play a major role in describing the importance given to training?

1.3 Hypothesis of the study

Hypothesis 1: Alternate Hypothesis H_a : Importance given to training is not uniform between employees based on their gender.

Hypothesis 2: Alternate Hypothesis H_a : Importance given to training is not uniform for employees based on their age groups.

Hypothesis 3: Alternate Hypothesis H_a : Importance given to training is not uniform for employees based on their educational qualifications

Hypothesis 4: Alternate Hypothesis H_a : Importance given to training is not uniform among employees based on their marital status

Hypothesis 5: Alternate Hypothesis H_a : Importance given to training is not uniform for employees based on their experience levels.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Training

Gaertner and Nollen, 1998, found that employee commitment is dependent on the perception employee develops towards the organization. Training is the best practice to promote optimistic thinking about organization among employees. Institute of employment studies researched many organizations to study the connection between employee engagement and training. According to the research, when employees are facilitated with effective training programs, the levels of employee outcomes in terms of job satisfaction, commitment, role clarity, and in-role performances are seen to be increased, leading to high intention to stay as engagement levels are advanced.

Employees of an organization are distinct in terms of their knowledge, skills, and talent levels. Making employees effectively use their competencies to achieve the organizational objective and improve their performance training is required. According to Armstrong (2006), training is termed as an approach of organization that accredits employees to accomplish their tasks. Virtually by gaining work-related knowledge and skills to contribute towards organizational success. Further, as stated by various authors and researchers, training enhances employee capacity and competencies required to perform the job duties. Also, Dessler, 2008 referred training as a method that enhances employee job skills. Organizations must consider the importance of training as it is an endeavor to improve employee skills in their present and future jobs, leading to enhanced performances. Also Jackson, 2000 supports the statement of other researchers. He stated that training is an effective tool for improving employee work efficiency, improving employee and organizational performances.

On the other hand, Brown 2005, said that training programs help attain a competitive and strategic position. It plays a considerable function in achieving the desired outcomes of the organization. Dobson & Tosh, 1998 stated that employers must change employee assumptions and notions through rigorous efforts. For changing the employee performances training is one of the suitable techniques. Huselid 1995 suggests that training helps monitor employee performance because the better the employees are aware and capable of the job that best are the consequences. A survey conducted on 552 hotel staff by Saanova et al.2003 investigated the relationship between training and employee engagement. They identified that there exists a positive relationship between the two. Training helps in increasing the employee work-related behaviors that lead to increased engagement and effective outcomes. It can be said that training is a driver of employee engagement as it boosts employee engagement levels.

Similarly, it is important to analyze the areas where the impact of training is positive. From the research of Jones et al. 2004, it can be noticed that there exists evidence that shows training helps in fostering employee stay intentions. Employees view training as a source of developing job related behaviours and knowledge that enhances employee commitment levels. Thus a well-designed training program is essential to improve individual specific and job-specific skill development. To experience greater productivity in terms of outcomes, training is a must.

2.2 Link between Demographic variables and organizational practices:

Outcomes of every research vary depending on the type of practices, the organizations initiate. When the organizations need to get the best use of its engagement practices it should also analyze the importance of each of these engagement practices. The importance given by employees is based on the demographic profile. Various researchers indicated that there are mixed results when a study is made on identifying the relationship between employee engagement and gender, at the same time, others have found that only women employees exhibit high levels of engagement, not on the least it is also sometimes seen that male employees show more engagement levels compared to female employees (Rothbard,1999). According to Gallup study, US research reported that women tend to find more job satisfaction and self-fulfillment when compared, and hence are more engaged than male employees(Johnson, 2004).

The Gallup report also indicated a significant difference in engagement levels of employees based on their marital status as it showed that unmarried employees are less engaged than married employees because a professional and settled life may be one of the reasons for this difference in engagement levels. Similarly, Swaminathan and Ananth, 2012 stated that employee engagement is influenced

significantly by employee demographic variables and analyzed that employees with higher income levels and more experience exhibit increased levels of commitment and loyalty towards work and organization, making their employee engagement levels to improve.

Mohapatra and Sharma (2010) described employee experience and employee engagement levels. They stated that there exists a positive relationship between the two variables as in the case with all other demographic variables like, age, gender, marital status, educational level, work experience etc hence the literature reviewed from the point of link between education level of employees and their engagement levels and stated that organizations can experience increased level of engagement when employees are with higher educational qualifications and further Avery et,al,2007 states that there is a positive link between employee engagement levels and the level of their experience because demographic variables like age, gender, educational qualification, marital status and experience give different employee outcomes, which means that employees with different demographic factors are getting engaged distinctly giving different outcomes hence it can be observed that changes in demographic variables directly shows an impact on employee engagement levels and to explain it in detail Avery, 2007 gave an example where organizations can experience increased engagement levels and outcomes when its employees are with high educational qualifications because they possess high capability and give preference towards accomplishment of work and also when employees are seen to be cognitively and emotionally satisfied they put extra efforts to go beyond their job descriptions for welfare of the organization

Overall, the above literature shows that the demographic variables are the causes for variations in employee engagement levels of employees. The employees' expectations differ from each other on how they will work and what their work-life balance will be. If employers are not successful in meeting their employee expectations, there will be a negative effect on employee engagement levels. It is therefore clear that irrespective of the type, the impact of demographic variables exists.

3.DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

3.1 DATA COLLECTION

Data for the study is collected through primary source i.e. questionnaire. Survey method is adapted for collecting primary data. Hence questionnaire is circulated to 325 employees of 40 Small to Mid-

sized IT companies in Hyderabad. A pilot survey was done to test the questionnaire using a smaller sample size (Convenience Sampling) compared to the planned sample size.

IBM SPSS version 23.0

Type of Population: Finite population

Sampling unit: Hyderabad, Telangana

Size of the sample: 299

Sampling procedure: Unrestricted Probability sampling

Sampling Technique: Simple random convenient sampling.

3.2 COMPUTATION OF FACTOR SCORES FOR THE EMPLOYEE ENGAGEMENT DRIVERS

3.2.1 Computation of Training Score

1. Confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) is a special form of factor analysis which is generally used to test whether measures of a construct (Questions created to operationalize the construct) are consistent with the nature of the construct. The main objective of CFA is to test whether the data fit a hypothesized measurement model.
2. Confirmatory Factor analysis (CFA) is performed taking importance given by the respondents towards training, their usage of training and their perception of training resulting into increased levels of engagement in terms of In-role performance, Increased job satisfaction, Increased intention to stay, Increase in role clarity and increased levels of organization citizenship behavior

Table-1 KMO Bartlett Test

KMO and Bartlett's Test		
Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.796
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	387.231
	Df	21
	Sig.	.000

Table-2 Computation of Training Score

Components	Initial Eigen values			Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	Variance %	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
	2.802	40.022	40.022	2.802	40.022	40.022
	0.960	13.711	53.733			
	0.828	11.829	65.563			
	0.727	10.386	75.948			
	0.655	9.358	85.307			
	0.572	8.171	93.477			
	0.457	6.523	100.000			
Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.						

KMO Measure of sampling adequacy value of 0.796 (>0.5) and p-value associated with Bartlett test of sphericity (<0.05) indicates that the operationalization of constructs is appropriate and the score computed through CFA can be used as a proxy to “Training” in the further analysis.

40% of the total variation in the overall data is explained by one component. This component is used as a proxy for Training score.

Table-3 The weightages given to questions on training

Component Matrix	
	Component
	1
Zscore(training)	0.555
Zscore(a)	0.597
Zscore(Training1)	0.704
Zscore(Training2)	0.594
Zscore(Training3)	0.668
Zscore(Training4)	0.637
Zscore(Training5)	0.661
Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.	

Almost all the questions carry equal weightages ranging from 56% to 70% in the positive direction

3.3 TESTING OF HYPOTHESIS 1

H_a: The importance given by employees towards training is not uniform based on gender.

3.3.1 Test Used

Independent sample t-test where the grouping variable is gender and the comparison variable is the normalized scores assigned to the importance given to Training,

Results

Table-4 Grouping Statistics

	Gender	N	Mean	Standard. Deviation
Zscore(training)	Female	66	-.1726	1.0906
	Male	233	.0489	.9697

Independent Sample t-test

		F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
Zscore(training)	Equal variances assumed	.818	.366	-1.593	297	.112
	Equal variances not assumed	-----	-----	-1.492	96.018	.139

3.4 TESTING OF HYPOTHESIS 2

H_a: The importance given by employees towards training is not uniform based on their age groups.

3.4.1 Test Used

One-way ANOVA along with Post hoc statistics where the grouping variable is Age group and the comparison variable is the normalized scores assigned to the importance to training,

Results

Table-5 Descriptive Statistics

		N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Zscore(training)	25-35 Years	230	.077	.967
	35-45 Years	61	-.310	1.093
	Above 45 Years	8	.142	.839

	Total	299	.000	1.000
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Test of homogeneity of variances

	Levene Statistic	df1	df2	Sig.
Zscore(training)	.714	2	296	.490

ANOVA Results

		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Significance.
Zscore(training)	Between Groups	7.406	2	3.703	3.772	.024
	Within Groups	290.594	296	.982		
	Total	298.000	298			

Robust tests of equality of means

		Statistical	df1	df2	Sig.
Zscore(training)	Welch	3.157	2	18.480	.066
	Brown-Forsythe	4.002	2	41.681	.026

Turkey Post hoc Tests

Dependent Variable: Zscore (Training)				
Tukey				
(I) Age	(J) Age	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.
25-35 Years	35-45 Years	.388*	.143	.019
	Above 45 Years	-.064	.356	.982
35-45 Years	25-35 Years	-.388*	.143	.019
	Above 45 Years	-.452	.373	.446
Above 45 Years	25-35 Years	.064	.356	.982
	35-45 Years	.452	.373	.446
*. The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level.				

3.4.2 Interpretation; Importance To Training

Descriptive statistics indicate that there are only 8 employees in the above 45 age category and may bias the result to some extent.

Mean score is slightly negative for 35-45 age group whereas it is slightly positive for other two age groups

Standard deviation is also slightly higher for 35-45 age groups compared to the other groups

Tests of homogeneity of variances do not reveal any significant difference in standard deviations (p-value = 0.49 > 0.05)

As the variances are not significantly different, ANOVA can be used to compare the means across the groups instead of robust tests of equality of the means.

ANOVA suggests that the differences in the mean importance given is significantly different across the groups (p-value = 0.024 < 0.05).

Tukey post-hoc test is performed as the variances are equal. This reveals that people in the age group 25-35 years give significantly more importance to training compared to people in 35-45 age group (p-value = 0.019 < 0.05). There is no significant difference between other groups.

3.5 TESTING OF HYPOTHESIS 3

H_a: The importance given by employees towards training is not uniform based on their educational qualifications.

3.5.1 Test Used

One-way ANOVA along with Post hoc statistics where the grouping variable is Educational qualification and the comparison variable is the normalized scores assigned to the importance to training.

Results

Tabl-6: Descriptive Statistics

		N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Zscore(training)	Graduation	196	.075	1.014
	Post-Graduation	88	-.155	.968
	Above PG	15	-.076	.947
	Total	299	.000	1.000

Test of homogeneity of variances

	Levene Statistic	df1	df2	Sig.
Zscore(training)	1.975	2	296	.141

ANOVA Results

		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Zscore(training)	Between Groups	3.301	2	1.650	1.658	.192
	Within Groups	294.699	296	.996		
	Total	298.000	298			

Robust tests of equality of means

		statistical	df1	df2	Sig.
Zscore(training)	Welch	1.677	2	38.174	.200
	Brown-Forsythe	1.767	2	60.634	.180

3.5.2 Interpretation; Importance To Training

Descriptive statistics indicate that there are only 15 employees in the above PG category and may bias the result to some extent.

Mean score is slightly positive for graduates whereas it is slightly negative for other two age groups. Tests of homogeneity of variances do not reveal any significant difference in standard deviations ($p\text{-value} = 0.141 > 0.05$).

As the variances are not significantly different, ANOVA can be used to compare the means across the groups instead of robust tests of equality of the means.

ANOVA suggests that the differences in the mean importance given is not significantly different across the groups ($p\text{-value} = 0.192 < 0.05$).

As the mean differences are not significant, post hoc tests are not necessary in this case.

3.6 TESTING OF HYPOTHESIS 4

Ha: The importance given by employees towards training is not uniform employees based on their marital status.

3.6.1 Test Used

Independent sample t-test where the grouping variable is marital status and the comparison variable is the normalized scores assigned to the importance to training.

Results

Table-7 Group Statistics

	Marital Status	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Zscore(training)	Single	104	.324	.882
	Married	183	-.129	.994

Table:-Independent Sample t-test

		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means		
		F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
Zscore(training)	Equal variances assumed	.272	.602	3.861	285	.000
	Equal variances not assumed			3.990	235.754	.000

3.6.2 Interpretation

- Descriptive statistics show that the mean value for training is positive for single and negative for married people indicating that unmarried people have given higher importance to training compared to that of the married ones.
- Statistical test for difference in the standard deviation (F value and the corresponding significance) between the groups reveal that the standard deviations are not significantly different for training between single and married people (All p-values > 0.05).
- Independent sample t-test for difference in mean ratings highlight that there is a statistically significant difference between single and married people in the importance given towards Training.

3.7 TESTING OF HYPOTHESIS 5

The importance given by employees towards each training, is not uniform based on their experience levels.

3.7.1 Test Used

One-way ANOVA along with Post hoc statistics where the grouping variable is Work experience level and the comparison variable is the normalized scores assigned to the importance to training.

Results

Table-8 Descriptive Statistics

		N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Zscore(training)	<3 Years	134	.031	.985
	3-5 Years	73	-.057	1.060
	> 5 Years	92	.000	.982
	Total	299	.000	1.000

Test of Homogeneity of Variances

	Levene Statistic	df1	df2	Sig.
Zscore(training)	.681	2	296	.507

ANOVA Results

		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Zscore (training)	Between Groups	.369	2	.185	.184	.832
	Within Groups	297.631	296	1.006		
	Total	298.000	298			

Equality of means-Robust tests

		Statistical	df1	df2	Sig.
Zscore(training)	Welch	.172	2	169.214	.842
	Brown-Forsythe	.180	2	246.735	.835

3.7.2 Interpretation; Importance to Training

Tests of homogeneity of variances do not reveal any significant difference in standard deviations across the groups (p-value = 0.507 > 0.05)

As the variances are not significantly different, ANOVA can be used to compare the means across the groups instead of robust tests of equality of the means.

ANOVA suggests that the differences in the mean importance given is not significantly different across the groups (p-value = 0.832 > 0.05).

As the mean differences are not significant, post hoc tests are not necessary in this case.

3.8 SUMMARY OF THE INFERENCES

Alternate Hypothesis	Decision
There is a significant difference in the importance given to training between males and females	Reject
There is a significant difference in the importance given to training among employees based on their age groups	Accepted
There is a significant difference in the importance given to training among people with different educational qualifications	Rejected
There is a significant difference in the importance given to training between single and married employees	Accepted
There is a significant difference in the importance given to training based on experience levels	Rejected

3.9 SUMMARY OF FINDINGS:

Findings for Importance given to training based on employee demographic profile

Hypothesis	Demographic Dimensions	Training
1	GENDER 1. Male 2. Female	Positive for both male and female employees
2	AGE: 1.25-35yrs 2. 35-45 yrs 3.Above 45yrs	1.Employees of age group 25-35 give more importance
3	EDUCATIONAL QUALIFICATION 1.Graduation 2.Post graduation 3.Above post graduation	1.Slightly positive for graduates 2. Slightly negative for other two group of employees.

4	MARITAL STATUS 1.Single 2.Married	1.Unmarried employees give more importance compared to married employee
5	EXPERIENCE <3yrs 3-5 yrs >5yrs	No significant difference based on experience of work

Table-9 Importance given to training based on gender:

Gender	Training
Male -233	Uniform
Female-66	Uniform

Table-10 Importance given to training based on age:

Age	Training
25-35 years-230	More important
35-45 years-61	Uniform
Above 45 years-08	Uniform

Table-11 Importance given to training based on educational qualification:

Age	Training
Graduation - 196	Uniform
Post graduation- 88	Uniform
Above post Graduation-	Uniform

15	
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Table-12 Importance given to training based on marital status

Marital Status	Training
Married-183	Uniform
Unmarried-116	More important

Table-13 Importance given to training based on experience

Years of Experience	Training
<3 years-134	Uniform
3-5 years-73	Uniform
>5 years-92	Uniform

4.SUGGESTIONS & CONCLUSION

Table 5, shows that employees at different age categories show a difference in the importance level towards training; this may be due to task variety and skill variety. Thus it is suggested that employers need to understand the underlying differences in working conditions based on age differences. Employees of age 25-35 show more importance towards training, which clarifies this category of employees **want** more exposure to work, knowledge, skill development, and **good** experience. Therefore, **organizations** need to build strategies by which employees can get experience in diverse fields and multiple work areas. **Organizations should** increase the number of training programs to get practical exposure to work, **increasing** their competency levels and engagement levels.

Table 6 exhibits that there are no significant differences for the importance given to training by employees in IT sectors based on educational qualifications, this suggests that organizations should build employees motivation, engagement, and work commitment levels based on educational qualifications as employees of different educational qualifications do not weigh employee engagement drivers differently, training is given equal importance irrespective of their educational qualifications. This makes organizations to make proper utilization of training practice and equally focus on every category of employee.

It is observed from the table 7 that unmarried employees give more importance to training, compared to that of married employees. **Organizations therefore** need to focus on providing better pay and rewards, initiate more best training programs. As the unmarried employees can more focus towards organizations due to less stress levels, which makes them more committed and engaged.

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